

Research Methods for Marketing

“Consumer Expectation on Purchasing Primark Product Due to the Ethical Retailing Practice”

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Executive Summary

Consumers are increasingly conscious of doing ethically. As a result, environmentally concerned customers need information about the product that illustrates the genuine environmental impact of their purchases. Primark wants to explore where they can go with more sustainable products for its customers, therefore this research aims to learn about their attitudes, behaviours, perspectives, and understanding of sustainable products. This research will perform a quantitative study using an online closed-ended questionnaire involving 400 participants ranging in age from 18 to 40. As a result, the research findings will help Primark establish a new sustainable product range.

Contents

Executive Summary..... 2

1. Introduction/background..... 4

2. Aim and objectives..... 4

3. Research strategy, design, and data analysis strategy..... 5

 3.1 Research strategy..... 5

 3.2 Research design..... 5

 3.1.1 Sampling..... 5

 3.1.2 Research instruments..... 5

 3.1.3 Data collection..... 5

 3.3 Analysis and presentation of findings..... 5

4. Limitations..... 5

5. Ethics..... 5

6. Conclusion..... 6

7. References..... 7

Appendix A: Example research instrument..... 8

Appendix B: Gantt chart..... 8

Appendix C: Research matrix..... 8

1. Introduction/background

Ethical shopping entails purchasing goods that are produced without harming people, animals, or the environment. Consumers purchase ethically to avoid supporting forced labour and to combat human trafficking, and they have a beneficial influence on the environment by purchasing items created using more environmentally friendly processes. And since the outset of the COVID-19 pandemic, ethical retail practices have been a hot topic not only in the UK but around the world.

When asked about their sustainable lifestyle behavior in 2021, about six in ten consumers in the United Kingdom (UK) had tried limiting their use of single-use plastic, making it the most common sustainable habit among UK individuals that year. 'Sustainable consumerism' has become somewhat of a buzzword in recent years, through an increased awareness of the importance of protecting and preserving our environment. Accordingly, many more UK shoppers are trying to shop in a more environmentally friendly way. In 2021, many UK consumers said they would be interested in buying eco-friendly if it was easier to do so. In fact, just over 30 percent of Gen X shoppers in the UK said they would purchase more sustainable fashion products if they were more widely available. (Statista, 2022)

Some people are motivated by ethical and environmental reasons to support local businesses and their community. The commitment to 'localism' is predicted to stay, reflected in the 6% increase in spend in local shops in 2020. (*Ethical Consumerism Report 2021*, 2021) People spent around £3.4bn in local shops during 2019, and as people continue to stay close to home, this figure is set to increase significantly in the future. Research has indicated that 60% of consumers have said that post-pandemic they expect to buy from local shops (compared to 40% shopping locally pre-Covid), giving a promising indication to independent retailers outside of major towns and cities for 2021 and beyond. (*Ethical Consumerism in the Pandemic*, 2020)

Primark has committed to making all of its clothes from recycled or more sustainably sourced materials within a decade, promising the strategy will not lead to price rises. The retailer has also pledged to make clothes that can be "recyclable by design" by 2027. Only a quarter of the clothing it sells is made from recycled or sustainably sourced materials. (Partridge, 2021)

When purchasing regularly purchased commodities such as food, clothes, and beauty products, the majority of customers now believe it is critical to shop for ethical products. As a result, retailers must do an excellent job of informing customers about any ethical activities.

2. Aim and objectives

The aim of this study is to gain a consumer's viewpoint on an organization's sustainability and ethical retailing practices. It's a quantitative analysis study since it's examined without prejudice to any particulars because it's based on a larger quantity of data, and it also provides us with a specific answer to the research question with an acceptable and clear questionnaire. Information can be collected more efficiently and conveniently such as through phone conversations, emails, social media, or one-on-one interviews. The main objective of this study is to see if customers have favourable or negative views about sustainability, as well as how their knowledge levels impact their viewpoints. Following other objectives are to measure if the target customers of Primark have different perspective of purchasing products due to the change of ethical practice and to test if the customer have positive or negative attitudes regarding sustainability, and how their levels of knowledge influence their perspectives.

3. Research strategy, design, and data analysis strategy

3.1 Research strategy

The primary goal of this research is to determine if customers have positive or negative perspectives regarding sustainability, as well as how their knowledge levels influence their opinions. This research will use a mixed methodological approach to execute a questionnaire-based survey as well as secondary sources. With an emphasis on Primark, a survey to gather consumer perception on a company's sustainability and ethical shopping practices.

The data collection will be gathered using a single approach, which is primary research using the quantitative method. This is because it is described as the application of mathematical and statistical methodologies in books and other forms of communication to demonstrate and characterize trends in diverse disciplines of knowledge (Vargas-Quesada & Moya Anegón, 2007).

The study will be undertaken as a primary research since it requires new information and real-time data. This will guarantee that PRIMARK receives accurate information in order to design the most effective marketing strategy possible.

3.2 Research design

The study will be conducted via online surveys, making it easier for target respondents to answer the questions. This is because to the huge cost reductions compared to face-to-face meetings, which can be costly due to printing, phone calls, and other expenditures. However, because the majority of people nowadays are online, we may need to provide incentives to encourage them (Cleave, 2021). Using online platforms via social media (such as Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp). Validity refers to correctly proving the link between two or more variables, and it requires research rigour and integrity.

3.1.1 Sampling

In this research it is used cluster sampling: probability based quantitative research sampling method that involves non-random selection of the sample from the entire population of Primark customers which are about approximately 21.3 million customers around the UK . (Smith, 2021). In this method, the study is based on demographic factors such as age, gender, and geography. This makes it very easy for a survey developer to generate useful inferences from the responses and then the collected data will be examined with Qualtrics: Online survey software & Insight Platform .

To begin, let us define who Primark's potential consumers are. They are ordinary people who enjoy bargains and obtaining the most value for their money. In order to better understand Primark's present target customers, four segmentations were utilised in this research, starting from Demographic; Millennials following by Gen Z and Gen X, both male and female of middle to higher class in society. Second, consumer behaviour; clients who are price and quality sensitive and discriminating in their buying, such as vegan, no leather, cotton only, and so on. Third, psychographic; someone concerned about environmental protection and interested in ethical and sustainable buying. Finally, the majority of customers are from the United Kingdom's urban centers. (2020 *Consumers Driving Change*, 2020)

3.1.2 Research instruments

The notion of sustainability consciousness is introduced in this study, which refers to an individual's experience and awareness of sustainable development. A sustainability consciousness questionnaire was developed based on the UNESCO definition of sustainable development. Sustainable development has four dimensions: society, environment, culture, and economics, all of which are interwoven rather than distinct. Sustainability is a way of thinking about the future that balances environmental, sociological, and economic concerns in the quest of a higher standard of living. (2015, Sustainable Development) SCQ (culture, economics, society, and environment) is a multidimensional tool that portrays sustainability as a complicated topic that demands a

comprehensive approach (integrating three pillars: economic, environmental and social issues and contemplating knowledge, attitudes and behaviour). (2020) Also by filling out the Sustainability Consciousness Questionnaire: The questionnaire for this study (2018) with closed-ended questions was developed after the theoretical development and empirical validation of an assessment instrument for stakeholders engaging in sustainable development. Based on the responses of 400 people in the United Kingdom. Qualtrics: Online survey software & Insight Platform . was used to analyse the information gathered from respondents.

The questions are hence generated with all the factors from above.

1. How many times a month on average do you go buy new clothes from Primark?

- a) 1 – 2
- b) 3 – 4
- c) 4 – 5
- d) 6+

2. When buying clothes, what is important to you? (Select all that apply)

- a) price
- b) it's on trend
- c) it's made from a sustainable material
- d) it's convenient

3. What is the main factor of purchasing an item from Primark?

- a) price
- b) quality
- c) recycle material
- d) for the good cause

4. What factors motivate you to choose environmentally friendly clothing?

- a) good quality
- b) being environmentalist
- c) save earth
- d) others, please specify

5. When you no longer want an item of clothing, do you

- a) throw it away
- b) sell (second shop)
- c) donate it
- d) give to your family members

6. Why do you shop in Primark?

- a) price
- b) quality
- c) quantity

d) sustainability

7. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark going eco-friendly retailing.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

8. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark producing more sustainable clothes with higher pricing.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

9. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark keeping the same price but less sustainable clothes.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

10. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark separating sustainable clothing with non-sustainable clothing with price accordingly.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

As seen below, these questions would lead the study to satisfy the research aim and objectives.

The aim of understanding a consumer's viewpoint on an organization's sustainability and ethical retailing practices focusing on Primark. And the objectives of seeing if customers have favourable or negative views about sustainability, as well as how their knowledge levels impact their viewpoints. Following to measure if the target customers of Primark have different perspective of purchasing products due to the change of ethical practice and to test if the customer have positive or negative attitudes regarding sustainability, and how their levels of knowledge influence their perspectives.

3.1.3 Data collection

The primary source for quantitative data will be an online survey, which will make it easier for target respondents to answer the questions, and the secondary source will be publish research to identify the key factors that influence Primark's customers' perspectives on sustainability, as well as how their knowledge levels influence their opinions.

For primary source for quantitative data collection using an online survey with the help of Qualtrics, the world's leading enterprise survey technology solution, has been providing online samples for over five years. Qualtrics partners with over 20 online panel providers to supply a network of diverse, quality respondents to our worldwide client base. Qualtrics Panels Team has completed over 15,000 projects across every industry vertical including travel, financial services, healthcare, retail, consumer goods, technology, and manufacturing both in the US and globally. (ESOMAR Qualtrics, 2014).

The respondents will be invited for the online survey questionnaire through sms, e-mail, social media ads, and one on one survey at the physical stores of Primark. Customers will get a short message through text message and email with a link to the Qualtrics online survey, in exchange for which they will receive discounts on their next Primark purchase. Will also be employing social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, as machine learning will target just consumers who follow Primark or have used the retailer's tags and hashtags to identify respondents, and will be sent to the Qualtrics online survey, with the same benefits as above. Finally, consumers who have purchased in shops around every branch in the UK area will receive a discount voucher for their next Primark purchase if they complete a one-on-one survey via Qualtrics online survey questionnaire.

The researcher aims to launch the pilot test to ensure that the questions were clear and easy to answer, so that it would provide an accuracy data that was valid and reliable. Pilot testing is a rehearsal of a research study, allowing to test the research approach with a small number of test participants before conducting the main study. Although this is an additional step, it may be the time best spent on any research project. Just like proper experiment design is a necessity, it is important to take the time to critique, test, and iteratively improve the research design, before the research execution phase. By doing so, the researcher can ensure that the user research runs smoothly, and dramatically improve the output from the study. (Ghag, 2022)

The researcher will also use published studies as a secondary source for data collecting. This information will be gathered prior to the research to help researchers determine the measure if the target customers of Primark have different perspective of purchasing products due to the change of ethical practice and to test if the customer have positive or negative attitudes regarding sustainability, and how their levels of knowledge influence their perspectives

Consumers' green products awareness is significant in indicating the way of the green products buying decision. This study aims to investigate the sources of consumers' awareness toward green products and its impact on purchasing decision. The data is collected from 300 respondents by survey method through a structured questionnaire. Convenience and judgmental sampling method are used. Data are analysed using frequency analysis, mean, standard deviation and regression analysis. The study has found that promotional activities on eco-friendly products and reference groups significantly influence consumers green products awareness. Majority of the respondents are aware of green products. This study also reveals that green products

awareness as the critical factor, which significantly affects consumers green purchasing decision. This paper can contribute to this green awareness issues. The company can be benefited knowing sources of green products awareness. Those it can aid green awareness development along with green products offer to consumers. (2018a)

Activities	May	June	July	August	September	October	November
Topic and Analysis							
Aim and objectives							
Research strategy, design and data analysis							
Conduct pilot test							
Conduct the actual survey							
Annalise the data and findings							
Final review							

Figure 1 Grantt Chart

As the above grant chart represent the timeline of a research, starting from May 1st to November 30th, 2022.

3.3 Analysis and presentation of findings

As the researcher has used close-ended questionnaires to collect the data, the answer from the respondents will be very precise to what has been asked by the researcher. As it is easier and quicker, measurable and comparable, gets better understanding through the answers from the respondents. And not much hassle of irrelevant answers from the respondents.

To begin, go to Qualtrics: Online survey software & Insight Platform, either using their own analysis tool or downloading it into SPSS, and compare the responses of the respondents, either visually with graphs of pie chart, bar, and other types of graphs, or numerically using statistics numbers. Analyzing data with graphic graphs is simple and attractive to the eyes.

The first step is to select a specific topic from a questionnaire, after which the colourful bar graph will be generated based on the respondents' responses. We may examine it in terms of statistics and as an image. If the graph be downloaded as an image, it may

be readily copied and pasted into a research paper with proper data. Furthermore, we may analyse each question from the survey one by one to obtain specific responses from the respondents. Finally, the graph or figures will be included in the presentation or included in a written report for Primark.

4. Limitations

A high sample size is frequently required for quantitative research. Large-scale study, however, is unfeasible due to a lack of resources. Responses are frequently reliant on a certain time period, which is in turn dependent on the variables that exist at that moment. A systematic questionnaire with closed-ended questions is used. It results in the study proposal's restricted outcomes. As a result, the outcomes may not always accurately reflect the real event. In addition, the respondents' response alternatives are constrained due to the researcher's selection. And also the analysis is complex, costly, and time-consuming to complete. A substantial percentage of responses is sufficient to reflect the target population.

5. Ethics

In the online survey, the researcher will inform the respondents from the beginning that their answer was anonymous and confidential. The researcher will ensure all the respondents personal will not be used in any other form than for the survey itself and will be deleted anytime in request of the respondents, if they do not wish their personal data to be with the organisation. And also making sure that all the personal data (if collected) will be deleted in the end of survey. Lastly, before starting the questionnaire survey, researcher will give a short brief on why the survey is being conducted and what outcomes a respondent be getting after the survey.

6. Conclusion

Because sustainable products are in high demand in every sector of the market, including the fashion industry, it's critical to understand whether Primark customers have positive or negative views about sustainability, as well as how their knowledge levels influence their attitudes toward purchasing sustainable products from the retailer. This study will provide a clear picture of what Primark customers believe about ethical retailing. The opinions of 400 respondents and the published research would provide a better insight of how Primark's customers see sustainable items. As a result, Primark will benefit from this research in the near future.

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Appendix A: Example research instrument

Questionnaire from the survey used in the Qualtrics for the data analysis:

1. How many times a month on average do you go buy new clothes from Primark?
 - a) 1 – 2
 - b) 3 – 4
 - c) 4 – 5
 - d) 6+

2. When buying clothes, what is important to you? (Select all that apply)
 - a) price
 - b) it's on trend
 - c) it's made from a sustainable material
 - d) it's convenient

3. What is the main factor of purchasing an item from Primark?
 - a) price
 - b) quality
 - c) recycle material
 - d) for the good cause

4. What factors motivate you to choose environmentally friendly clothing?
 - a) good quality
 - b) being environmentalist
 - c) save earth
 - d) others, please specify

5. When you no longer want an item of clothing, do you
 - a) throw it away
 - b) sell (second shop)
 - c) donate it
 - d) give to your family members

6. Why do you shop in Primark?
 - a) price
 - b) quality
 - c) quantity

d) sustainability

7. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark going eco-friendly retailing.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

8. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark producing more sustainable clothes with higher pricing.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

9. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark keeping the same price but less sustainable clothes.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

10. On scale of 1 to 5. Primark separating sustainable clothing with non-sustainable clothing with price accordingly.

5 being the highest.

1 2 3 4 5

Appendix B: Gantt chart

Activities	May	June	July	August	September	October	November
Topic and Analysis							
Aim and objectives							
Research strategy, design and data analysis							
Conduct pilot test							
Conduct the actual survey							
Annalise the data and findings							
Final review							

Appendix C: Research matrix

Objectives:	Hypothesis:	Variables:	Technical analysis:	Conclusion:
to gain a consumer's viewpoint on an organization's sustainability and ethical retailing practices	this study will give an clear understanding on sustainable retailing from customers' perspective	4 segmentation: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Demographic,• Psychographic• Behavioural• Geographical,	Qualtrics: online survey for the questionnaire	Consumers are increasingly conscious of doing ethically